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D3.1 – Report on taxonomy of sectoral entry points related to rapid technological innovation and behavioural changes

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1. Changes with respect to the description of work

No changes to deliverable scope.

2. Dissemination and uptake

This deliverable is public and will be available at ELEVATE's website.

3. Short summary of results (<250 words)

This deliverable reports the activities conducted under Task 3.1 and Task 3.2 of the ELEVATE project.

In Task 3.1 a machine learning-assisted systematic literature review is conducted to answer the research question: Which combinations of policy instruments and enabling factors are identified in the literature as contributing to the successful deployment of mitigation technologies or transitioning away from fossil fuels? This task provides an overview of best practice policy cases accounting for central enabling factors. These cases are then clustered by common combinations of policy instruments and enablers, revealing key climate policy strategies and their supportive contexts that can serve as role models and offer valuable insights.

A comprehensive literature review by van den Berg et al. (2023) provides key insights into aspects of behavioural change, presented in Task 3.2. The review clarifies essential terminology relevant to behaviour changes, offering a clear framework for understanding the various concepts involved. It identifies a range of entry points for implementing behaviour changes, along with the enabling factors that facilitate these shifts.

Tasks 3.3 and 3.4, which are beyond the scope of this deliverable, will build on the foundation laid here. The assessments by Task 3.1 and 3.2 will be further enriched by the political economy analysis of Task 3.3. Subsequently, Task 3.4 will explore how political economy constraints as well as sectoral technology and behavioural entry points can be translated into a modelling framework.

4. Evidence of accomplishment

See report below.

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1. Introduction

This deliverable reports the activities carried out under Task 3.1 and Task 3.2 of the ELEVATE project. The tasks description in the proposal is as follows:

Task 3.1: Taxonomy of sectoral entry points related to rapid technological innovation

This task will conduct a systematic evaluation of sector-specific technological entry-points for deep emission reductions. Promising candidates for entry points with a strong systemic effect and a record of successful examples are the decarbonization of power generation, ensuing electrification of end-uses, and low-carbon fuels for hard-to electrify sectors, like aviation and shipping. Other candidates are efficiency improvement and impacts of structural changes (e.g. more recycling). Based on this analysis, we will develop a taxonomy of sector and technology entry points, classifying them along various dimensions, including technology readiness, scalability, policy requirements, systemic effects, etc. The evaluation of entry points will consider the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on post-pandemic sector trends and the ability for policy intervention.

Task 3.2: Taxonomy of entry-points related to behavioural changes

This task will conduct a systematic evaluation of sector-specific behavioural entry-points for deep emission reductions, such as less carbon-intensive lifestyles. The focus is on urban mobility services and residential buildings as they interact with the options from Task 3.1. Such behavioural changes depend on complex internal agent factors (e.g. ability/willingness of individuals to carry out certain actions) and intricate external influences (e.g. political and institutional landscapes, social networks, gender and market prices) that need to be aligned with policy interventions. We will conduct a literature evaluation of behavioural changes in the specified sectors focusing on government perspectives for action. This task will deliver a taxonomy of behavioural- and sector-specific entry-points classifying these entry points into different categories. The analysis of entry points will also consider the impacts of the COVID-19 pandemic on lifestyles and demand patterns.

A prior objective is to establish a shared terminology between the two tasks and ensure a common understanding for technological and behavioural entry points to deep decarbonization at the sectoral level. To this end, we introduce some key concepts. First, we define climate policies as *effective* if they lead to a desired outcome. The desired outcome is the increase in deployment of mitigation technologies or the transition away from fossil fuels (task 3.1), or the behavioural change (task 3.2). *Enabling factors*, when present, contribute to the effectiveness of these policy instruments or their implementation, while their absence can create

barriers (Montfort et al., 2023). We refer to the alignment between an effective climate policy and its supporting context as an “*entry point*”.

In Task 3.1 a machine learning-assisted systematic literature review is conducted to answer the research question: Which combinations of policy instruments and enabling factors are identified in the literature as contributing to the successful deployment of mitigation technologies or transitioning away from fossil fuels? This task provides an overview of best practice policy cases, accounting for central enabling factors. These cases are then clustered by common combinations of policy instruments and enablers, revealing key climate policy strategies and their supportive contexts that can serve as role models and offer valuable insights. In addition, the entry point overview can inform integrated assessment modelling efforts, providing a rationale and direction for the roll-out of best practice policies.

A comprehensive literature review by van den Berg et al. (2023) provides key insights into aspects of behavioural change, presented in Task 3.2. The review clarifies essential terminology relevant to behaviour changes, offering a clear framework for understanding the various concepts involved. It identifies a range of entry points for implementing behaviour changes, along with the enabling factors that facilitate these shifts.

The findings from van den Berg et al. (2023) have been compiled into a spreadsheet and further enriched with examples, based on the harmonized entry point framework. This is summarized [here](#).

The assessment by Task 3.1 and 3.2 will be further enriched by the political economy analysis of Task 3.3. Subsequently, Task 3.4 will explore how political economy constraints as well as sectoral technology and behavioural entry points can be translated into a modelling framework. This includes a new approach with SLIM (Sustainable Living In Modelling) scenario narratives developed by van den Berg et al. (2023), which serve as a next step toward better integrating lifestyle change into Integrated Assessment Modelling (IAM).

Modelling efforts that provide a method to represent technological and behavioural entry points as well as the impact of political economy constraints (D3.2) in IAM scenarios will be further developed in Task 3.4. In line with the project timeline, these modelling advances will be incorporated into the modelling protocol of the synthesis work of WP6.

2. Taxonomy of sectoral entry points related to rapid technological innovation

2.1. Background

Despite success in setting a goal for 1.5°C in the Paris Climate Agreement, there remains a significant gap between climate policy ambition and real-world implementation. Fransen et al. (2023) highlight two critical components of this “implementation gap”. First, the policy adoption gap, which describes the discrepancy of emission goals and implemented policy instruments. Second, the policy outcome gap, representing the difference between the intended emission reduction level of the implemented policy instrument and the emission reduction archived. Whether a climate policy is implemented and effectively influences the deployment of climate mitigation technologies varies depending on various contexts and jurisdictions.

In economic literature, carbon pricing is viewed as economically most efficient and thus the first-best solution to tackle climate change related externalities (Bennear and Stavins, 2007). However, political economy factors (e.g., lobbying seeking for loopholes, crowding in/out, vested interest) can constraint policy implementation and justify the use of multiple policy instruments in a second-best world (Jenkins, 2014). Nonetheless, carbon pricing remains a central climate policy option (Baranzini et al., 2017) and is applied in more than 70 pricing schemes worldwide (World Bank, 2023). From an empirical perspective, Stechemesser et al. (2024) provide a possible explanation for the simultaneous need for a well-defined policy mix as well as a concentration on the implementation and strengthening of carbon pricing. Assessing the effectiveness of climate policies across 41 countries, they find that the majority (70%) of climate policies is effective as combination of two or more policies and carbon taxation belongs to the few exceptions that causes large emission breaks as single policy instrument. The probability of climate policy implementation (Jewell et al., 2019) as well as the policy outcome (Döbbling-Hildebrandt et al., 2024; Jakob et al., 2020) appear to critically depend on the regional context factors¹. For instance, Levi et al. (2020) find that carbon prices are primarily implemented in regions with well-governed political institutions and a general awareness of human-caused climate change.

Conclusive research on climate policies that account for context factors tends to either have a narrow focus or rely on classifications that lack regional peculiarities. For instance, some literature primarily concentrates on enabling factors in specific sectors or regions (Bhatia, 2023; Lu et al., 2020; Ohlendorf et al., 2022; Safarzadeh et

¹ Only 69 out of around 1,500 policies evaluated by Stechemesser et al. (2024) are effective in terms of causing emission breaks.

al., 2020; Thapar et al., 2016; Trosvik et al., 2023). On a broader, global scale, Brutschin et al. (2021) structure the feasibility dimensions of low carbon transition scenarios and Montfort, Fesenfeld, and Ingold (2023) establish a general typology of barriers and enablers of ambitious climate mitigation policies. Implementing best practice policies requires a deeper understanding of the regional context, as the resulting technology change can depend on the current national stage, e.g., share of technology, energy strategy or further macroeconomic peculiarities (Jewell et al., 2019; Ohlendorf et al., 2022).

We aim to fill this gap and identify the combination of climate policies and regional enabling context factors for central energy and demand technologies. Policy instruments include a broad portfolio of economic and regulatory instruments, information and climate strategies as well as investments and policy targets (Callaghan et al., 2024; van den Bergh et al., 2021). Enabling factors, when present, contribute to the effectiveness of these policy instruments or their implementation, while their absence can create barriers (Montfort et al., 2023). In essence, we aim to better understand with an ex-post perspective the connection of effective climate policies – those that either accelerate the deployment of mitigation technologies or facilitate the transition away from fossil fuels – to the specific regional factors that enabled them. We refer to the alignment between an effective climate policy and its enabling context as an "*entry point*".

Our research question is: Which combinations of policy instruments and enabling factors are identified in the literature as contributing to the deployment of mitigation technologies or transitioning away from fossil fuels? We look across geographies and sectors. Thereby, we aim to develop a taxonomy of technological entry-points for deep-decarbonization at the sectoral level. This systematic literature review addresses a critical gap in the literature by synthesizing empirical evidence on the interplay of policy interventions and enabling factors. Our focus is on ex-post evaluations of policies in the literature published in the aftermath of the Paris Climate Agreement, covering energy as well as final demand sectors. We employ a mixed-method approach which incorporates machine learning to identify relevant papers from a large body of literature, followed by qualitative human extraction and processing from the selected articles. For each best practice policy case presented in the literature that also accounts for enabling factors, we extract the policy instrument applying the classification by Callaghan et al. (2024) and the enabling factors are categorized based on the feasibility framework by Brutschin et al. (2021). These cases are then clustered by common combinations of policy instruments and enablers, revealing key climate policy strategies and their enabling contexts that can serve as role models and offer valuable insights.

Our inquiry is essential due to its contribution in two key areas. Primarily, we provide an overview of best practice policy cases, accounting for central enabling factors. Furthermore, we highlight specific contextual factors by clustering the technological entry points, e.g., along political motivation, development status and governance. Thereby, we provide policymakers with a practical summary for identifying and leveraging context-specific opportunities for sectoral decarbonization. Second, we can inform integrated assessment modelling efforts, providing a rationale and direction for the roll-out of best practice policies. While integrated assessment models (IAMs) are central for informing climate policy (Bosetti, 2021; Weyant, 2017), they face challenges to account for contextual factors relevant for policy success (De Cian et al., 2020; Jewell and Cherp, 2020; van Sluisveld et al., 2020). Such context includes institutions, public support, economic structures and political structures.

2.2. Research method

We employ a machine learning assisted systematic literature review to answer our primary research question: Which combinations of policy instruments and enabling factors are identified in the literature as contributing to the successful deployment of mitigation technologies or transitioning away from fossil fuels? Our sample selection process in Figure 1 follows the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) framework developed by Moher et al. (2010).

Figure 1: Sample selection process

To identify potentially relevant articles, we first developed a broad search string using the SPIDER framework as presented by Cooke et al. (2012) (see Table OA 1). We search the databases Scopus and Web of Science using the search string in Table OA 2 and filter for publication dates in or after 2015, the year of the decision on the Paris Climate Agreement. This yields a total of 7,997 unique, potentially relevant articles. In a next step, we refine the screening for articles relevant to the research question and scope of this review. The identified articles are selected for their eligibility subject to the following inclusion criteria:

1. Study includes an effective climate policy regarding technology deployment or phase-out²;
2. Study includes context-specific enablers for the policy intervention or context-specific barriers that the policy intervention is based on;
3. Study analyses technologies in one or more of the following focus sectors of this review: energy, transport, industry, buildings or carbon management;
4. Study is not a single method literature review; and
5. Study uses an empirical ex-post evaluation method (qualitative or quantitative).

To operationalize the screening for these criteria, we use a two-step process: A machine learning assisted title and abstract screening followed by a human only full paper screening. The screening at the title and abstract level is supported by an active learning algorithm, the language processing model DistilRoBERTa³. As the authors take a human-based decision on whether an article is likely to meet the inclusion criteria or not, the algorithm ranks remaining studies in order of relevance. Using a conservative stopping criterion through ranked quasi-sampling developed by Callaghan and Müller-Hansen (2020), we screen until we identify at least 90 percent of relevant articles with a level of confidence that is above 95 percent (the screening is stopped at a p value of 0.023⁴). Overall, we manually screen 2,924 article abstracts and titles and 5,073 are excluded automatically by the active learning algorithm (see Figure OB 2). Of the screened articles, 207 are classified as potentially relevant. After a manual full paper screening 89 articles are identified as relevant and extracted (see Table OB 1). Based on a detailed article assessment we code the central elements: geography, research method, enablers and the effective climate mitigation policy. The majority of the articles are case studies (see Figure OB 2) that state the policy effectiveness based on expert interviews or surveys.

² In the literature it is clearly stated that the policy induced a technology deployment change, supported either by statistical analysis or by insights from expert judgements or interviews.

³ See: <https://huggingface.co/distilroberta-base>.

⁴ With a confidence of 97.7 percent, we identify at least 90 percent of relevant articles.

Figure 2: Regional coverage of effective climate mitigation policies

Note. The geographical representation covers national policies, international policies (e.g., EU) and state policies.

In total, we identify 115 entry points. The majority of assessments (35%) focused on China, Germany, and the UK, with China accounting for 22 reported cases. In the Global South as well as in the Middle East and North Asia, effective climate policy cases are barely reported in our sample.

Figure 3: Sector and technology coverage

Note. The sector and technology coverage rely on targeted technologies of the effective sectoral climate mitigation policy cases and thus sums above the total number of articles.

We assign the identified technologies to the sectors (see Figure 3). With 86.1%, the majority belongs to the energy sector, 9% to transport, 3.5% to buildings and 1.4% to carbon management. Although we explicitly searched for effective industrial policies in our search terms (see Table OA 2), no such case fulfilled our inclusion criteria. The articles that evaluate climate policies in the industrial sector focus on energy efficiency⁵ improvements, which fall outside the scope of this research. Some effective policy cases described in the literature are directly linked to the specific induced policies (see

Figure 4).

Figure 4: Timeline of select policies

⁵ Increase in energy efficiency tend to result in a rebound effect, increasing productivity and consumption (Millward-Hopkins et al., 2020) with uncertain final effects regarding technology deployment and emission (A. Greening et al., 2000; Brännlund et al., 2007; Wei and Liu, 2017).

Note. The policies presented are limited to cases where the policy is mentioned directly in the article.

In our synthesis we categorize enabling factors along the feasibility framework by Brutschin et al., (2021) (see Figure 5). Most of the extracted enabling factors fall into either economic or social categories. However, institutional capacity is cited most frequently as an enabler, followed by interest group support and market structure. In the energy sector, market structure refers to decoupling of electricity generation, distribution and transition as well as liberalization and cross border renewable trade. In line with arguments for policy sequencing (Meckling et al., 2017), we find that carbon pricing functions not only as a policy instrument but also as an enabler for other policy measures.

Figure 5: Categorization of enabling factors

Note. The overview presents the most frequent enablers that are extracted three or more times and allocated to the feasibility dimension by the Brutschin et al. (2021) framework.

The extracted policy instruments are structured following the policy categories of the Climate Policy Database (2024), Callaghan (2024) and Nascimento et al. (2022). To gain deeper insights into various strategies and regional contexts, we conduct an entry point clustering analysis.

To provide a comprehensive overview, we use a clustering scheme by first identifying the main dimensions of the differences in entry points that form the basis for clustering. The dimensions include the level of economic development, the framework of governance, and the primary motivation of the policymakers (see Figure 6). These dimensions are selected based on their explanatory power and their contextual relevance for the questions of our study.

Figure 6: Cluster classification

Further refinement of the clusters is based on contextual information like the types of policy instruments used, the enablers that are in common and challenges specific to the technology. Based on the identified clusters, we assigned each entry point to a cluster. The categories renewables, solar and wind (where articles concentrate primarily on solar and wind) display considerable overlap and homogeneity, motivating our decision to combine the three together for clustering and processing. Consequently, we organized clusters within the energy groups – bioenergy, coal and renewables (results, see OD. 1) – and the demand sectors, including buildings and transport (results, see OD. 2).

The number of identified entry points varies significantly across groups. Among renewables, we identified 65 entry points, reflecting the largest technology group. To identify the enablers and policy interventions most relevant for the renewable cluster, we trained a random forest classifier to predict the most important enablers and entry points for each cluster from the raw data of the extractions. A random-forest classifier is selected for a few reasons: One, it can represent complex non-linear associations, and it is robust to overfit and can handle small samples. It works by creating a large ensemble of decision trees, where each decision tree is a combination of certain features, it then samples this ensemble of trees to make a final prediction (Breiman, 2001). In our case, the features are enablers and policy instruments, which are assigned 1 when present and 0 when absent. To ensure that the model accurately

captures the relationship between clusters and features, we employ a cross validation, which tests the model by omitting one data point from its training data and comparing its performance (Wong, 2015). This is done for every data point until the model performs consistently well (see results Table OC 1).

The other groups – bioenergy, buildings, coal and transport– comprise a substantial portion of the sample, though fewer entry points are identified within them. Each group is processed separately, assigned clusters, and analysed independently, without prioritization by the random forest identifier.

A number of technologies, such as carbon management, grid storage, hydroelectricity and nuclear are not sufficiently investigated within our sample, thus contain too few data points for entry point-based clustering. Consequently, entry points for these technologies are presented at technology level (see Figure OD 3).

2.3. Results

The presented sectors and technologies for the entry point clustering include renewables, transitioning away from coal and zero emission vehicles (see Table 1). Further description regarding the clustering of within bioenergy and buildings as well as additional information on less studied technologies are presented in OD 1-3.

Table 1: Categorization of sectoral technology entry points

Cluster	Description	Central Strategy	Examples	
Renewables deployment	Instrumentalists	Economies leveraging existing financial markets, taxation and regulatory instruments for streamlined and efficient renewable energy deployment.	Strategies focus on utilizing advanced financial instruments, such as tax credits, green bonds, and private equity mechanisms, to create optimal conditions for investment. They prioritize minimizing regulatory friction and maximizing investor confidence.	United Kingdom, United States
	Strategists	Economies employing long-term, carefully planned policy incentives and investments to enhance renewable energy uptake through coordinated stakeholder collaboration and institutional capacity building. The approach is horizontal and multi-pronged with an emphasis on institutional capacity.	Policies feature a balanced approach that utilizes a combination of subsidies, R&D investments, and coordinated policy interventions. Enabled by interest group support, distributional effects, and robust fiscal strategies.	Austria, Germany, Ireland, Portugal
	Regional Autonomy	Political systems with substantial sub-national control, focusing on empowering regional actors and fostering localized renewable energy solutions.	Policy approach emphasizes local decision-making with regional subsidies, localized grid integration, and community-based energy projects. Supports renewable deployment through regional regulatory autonomy and tailored energy initiatives.	Italy, Scotland, Sweden

	Cluster	Description	Central Strategy	Examples
Renewables deployment	Planners	Centrally planned or coordinated economies employing a top-down framework to drive renewable deployment through consolidated planning and state-backed investment, often led by public sectors.	Features strong government-led initiatives, involving direct state ownership of energy assets, extensive use of public sector utilities, and integrated multi-year planning for renewable targets. Utilizes government-linked financial institutions to mobilize funding.	China, South Korea, Vietnam
	Adaptive Pragmatists	Emerging markets employing flexible and innovative policy tools to implement renewable energy solutions while prioritizing cost reduction and overcoming limited institutional frameworks.	Employs auction-based renewable energy tenders, risk-sharing mechanisms, and ad-hoc policy experimentation. Prioritizes minimizing costs through competitive bidding processes and leveraging partnerships to offset institutional limitations.	Brazil, India, South Africa
	Financial Cross-Cutters	Special cases where financial sector expertise predominantly drives renewable energy investment through structured capital flow, risk mitigation, and cost efficiency.	Relies heavily on financial intermediaries, such as national development banks, to structure capital flows. Employs risk mitigation instruments like guarantees, transnational financial partnerships, and green finance to reduce capital costs for renewable projects.	California, Germany, Senegal

	Cluster	Description	Central Strategy	Examples
Transitioning away from coal	Coal Dependent & Climate Advocate	Developed economies with a high share of coal in their energy mix and strong commitments to international climate goals.	Policy pledges are driven by environmental impact and proactive climate goals, with institutional capacity strengthened through stakeholder commissions.	Canada, Germany
	Liberalized & Coal Independent	Liberalized market, in which the already low share of coal declined further due to its substitutability with gas.	Rather weak opposition to phase-out has facilitated the pledge, driven by environmental concerns, social activism, and a focus on international reputation.	United Kingdom
	Financially Supported	Emerging economy with limited financial capacity for new coal power plants, making external funding crucial for transitioning away from coal.	International financial support is the primary enabler of the coal phase-out pledge, further supported by environmental impact concerns.	Vietnam
Net zero emission vehicle deployment	Green Innovators	Regions with a high share of EV sales combined with the absence of a strong conventional automotive industry and a high renewable share in the electricity-mix.	Enabled by the absence of a strong opposition and the presence of support coalitions and skill spillovers, policies include robust ZEV deployment strategies, such as ICEV sales bans, driven by emission reduction and economic growth opportunities.	California, Norway, Quebec
	Heavily State-Subsidized Transition	Planned economy, characterized by the world's highest absolute EV sales and a strong conventional automotive industry.	Driven by energy security, pollution concerns, and economic opportunities. Policies focus on subsidies, R&D, and non-financial demand-side incentives, including exemption from licence plate lotteries.	China
	Starters and Niche-Testers	Developed Economy with early but limited EV adoption.	Initial success driven by extraordinary funding, strong public acceptance, and renewable energy integration.	Estonia

2.3.1. Renewables: Solar and wind

Technological advancements in solar and wind have consistently driven down risks and costs while increasing efficiency. This progress can be partially attributed to Germany's early adoption of renewable energy technologies with its generous subsidy regime (Rechsteiner, 2020), which is later amplified by China's large-scale industrial policy efforts to boost renewable energy manufacturing, creating massive cost reductions in the technologies (Andrews-Speed, 2015; Dent, 2015).

Within the renewable technology deployment, we identify six distinct clusters. To enhance the clarity and visualization we present them in two sets. The first set consists of three clusters that primarily capture advanced economies. In contrast, the second set consists of two clusters that rather capture middle income and emerging economies as well as one intersectional cluster that reflects financial entry points.

Among the first set earlier forays into renewable energy (RE) policy are observed, with regions starting as early as the 1990s (Andrews-Speed, 2015; Rechsteiner, 2020; Shrimali et al., 2015). This is coupled with a wider set of entry points, reflecting the experimentation phases. Other common enablers include high public acceptance and support for renewables, and a political environment that prioritizes environmentally friendly measures (see Figure 7).

Figure 7: Entry points for renewables – Set: Advanced economies

Note. The presented entry points are selected by the random forest identifier by their feature importance. It reflects the predictive power of the entry point in determining the mitigation strategy cluster.

The **instrumentalists** cluster consists of regions like the United Kingdom (UK), and the United States of America (USA). They are united by their use of instrument regulatory, financial, and tax instruments to incentivize renewables, while minimizing direct government intervention and expenditure. Renewable portfolio standards (RPS) or similar quota-based systems are common choices. In the USA, RPS policy is a main driver for renewables growth, they target state run utilities and are amplified by federal support measures like production tax credits. Sophisticated financial markets enable tax credit policies to leverage financial actors for financing and risk reduction (Ameli et al., 2017; Zhang, 2023; Zhou and Solomon, 2020). The state of California tackles regulatory and entry barriers for homeowners, through a simplified approval process, resulting in increased residential solar installations (Hsu, 2018). The UK similarly has experimented with different measures leading to a technology neutral Renewable Obligation Certificate (ROC), which offers different levels of support based on technological maturity (Andrews-Speed, 2015).

Strategists are a collection of regions with advanced economies, strong institutional capacities and a strategic effort to boost renewable energy deployment at a federal level. They feature more multi-pronged political interventions via laws and programs in addition to fiscally robust subsidy mechanisms. The most important interventions include Feed-in Tariffs (FiTs), which pay fixed rates for a long contract period, with procurement guarantees for producers (Strunz et al., 2016). The presence of a large network of smaller heterogeneous of power producers is a key enabler allowing FiTs to have a wide impact. Interest group support and a stable policy enable consistent long-term progress in renewable energy deployment.

Germany is the archetypical example among this cluster. Its transition effort, known as “Energiewende”, demonstrates a long-term strategic effort to create an emissions avoidance industry, through a bottom-up technology-neutral FiT policy with long duration and high rates (Rechsteiner, 2020). Across German states, the involvement of the Green Party in state government of financially developed states or modernization strategies of states with high renewable expansion potential and lower financial development are influential factors for renewable energy deployment (Wurster and Hagemann, 2019, 2018). The costs of German FiT policy are primarily passed along to consumers, a strategy that may be challenging to replicate in other regions.

Other European members of this cluster include Austria, Ireland, and Portugal. In both the Portuguese case and the Austrian, the costs for FiTs are not passed along to consumers, rendering the cost-effectiveness of the policy in question (Peña et al., 2017; Wurster and Hagemann, 2019).

The cluster of **regional autonomy** is a set of national and sub-national regions characterized by devolved governance structures. Local authorities have considerable

power and accountability to locals, particularly when facing challenges related to wind power. The space intensive characteristics of wind, along with its noise and visual pollution effects, can elicit opposition from locals. Gaining public support is essential for success (Cowell et al., 2017; De Laurentis and Pearson, 2021).

Policy interventions like land use consenting via public private agreements can increase fairness and equity in project planning and execution, mitigating local opposition to new projects (De Laurentis and Pearson, 2021; Giest, 2015). Emphasizing co-benefits of RE like employment and economic growth, through professional training and narrative construction, also can boost public support.

The devolved governance structure allows for tailored policy interventions for the local context. Regulatory streamlining shows how local authorities can shape regulations to simplify the process and make it more specific. In the Scottish case, the One-Stop-Shop for wind energy simplified the approvals process. It is enabled by sustained political consensus and policy entrepreneurship. Existing industry expertise can also be of benefit, for instance Scotland's offshore oil and gas industry enabled skill transfer into offshore wind (Cowell et al., 2017; O'Hanlon and Cummins, 2020).

Compared to the first set, economies of the second set (see Figure 8) show a later start of renewables policy implementation. Most of the economies are in transition and rather belong to middle income and emerging economies. One exception constitutes of the financial cross-cutters that is an intersectional cluster with a focus on financial entry points.

Figure 8: Entry points for renewables – Set: Transitioning economies and financial cross-cutters

Note. The presented entry points are selected by the random forest identifier by their feature importance. It reflects the predictive power of the entry point in determining the mitigation strategy cluster.

Planners features countries with a strong executive and extensive state involvement in the energy sector. These create an enabling framework of a concentrated market guided by the state, with high institutional capacity and interest group support. In contrast to strategists, planners rather follow a top-down approach to policy making, with more direct interventions via state investments.

This is particularly true for China, where the state is involved in the energy sector and the supply chain for renewable energy (Dent, 2015; Gao and Yuan, 2020). Other members include South Korea (Kim, 2021; Kim et al., 2018) and Vietnam, with Vietnam currently making considerable progress in its solar photovoltaic (PV) deployment. (Do et al., 2021, 2020).

The core policy interventions include a FiT system with generous price guarantees (no procurement guarantees) without passing the costs to consumers. In China, this is complimented with renewable portfolio shares targeted at utilities companies, national development bank lending and state subsidies. These measures address investment risk, access to capital and coordinated market activity (Andrews-Speed, 2015; Dent, 2015; Gao and Yuan, 2020; Zhang, 2023, 2020). In Vietnam, FiTs are used on a shorter timescale along with higher rates for solar installations. In addition, regulatory interventions are made to enable easier land-leasing, private sector investment and grid connection.

Adaptive pragmatists are a set of regions broadly corresponding to emerging markets. These countries see renewable energy as an opportunity to tackle economic development, energy security, and sustainability. They face challenges in availability and access to financing, institutional capacity, skill, and knowledge gaps. They have high dependency on fossil fuels, where renewables reflect capacity additions rather than energy substitutions (Bradshaw and de Martino Jannuzzi, 2019; Kruger and Eberhard, 2018; Shidore and Busby). Members include countries like Brazil, Chile, India, Ghana and South-Africa. Among policy interventions, auction systems are used in innovative ways to reach cost-reduction, risk mitigation and capture local benefits. These are coupled with infrastructure investments and institutional creation. Brazil, for instance, innovated with technology-specific auctions for wind energy, which allowed for better prices and competition among bidders. This is further supported by an emphasis on creating local employment opportunities (Bradshaw and de Martino Jannuzzi, 2019; Costa et al., 2022).

South Africa pioneered with its auction design, which involved extensive project due-diligence criteria, along with local-socio-economic benefit provisions (Eberhard and Kåberger, 2016; Kruger and Eberhard, 2018; Matsuo and Schmidt, 2019). India's solar auctions are complemented with infrastructure investments (Shidore and Busby; Thapar et al., 2018). An innovative approach is observed in Ghana, leveraging public

private partnerships by using a fee for service scheme, to overcome high upfront costs via monthly instalments. This is coupled with a solar testing and training centre to enhance technological knowledge and expertise. (Amankwah-Amoah and Sarpong, 2016).

Unlike the other clusters, **financial cross cutters**, as their name implies, is an intersectional cluster of financial entry points. Members range from China to Germany and Senegal. They apply financial mechanisms to create entry points. They form a special case where the dominant policy actors are financial institutions and intermediaries functioning at a multi-lateral level.

A prominent feature is the presence of national development banks, including Brazil's BNDES, China's CDB and Germany's KfW, which all play a pivotal role in their respective countries energy transitions (Geddes et al., 2018; Isah et al., 2023; Zhang, 2020). For example, Germany's KfW provides cheap long-term debt, co-financed with local banks and offered knowledge sharing on RE project development and finance (Zhang, 2020). Similarly, BNDEs facilitated bulk lending for initial RE deployment, offering loans up to 80% of the project costs at favourable rates (Isah et al., 2023). These national development banks thus transform the risk profile of renewable investment and enabled private investment by providing assurance and risk management, particularly in the early stages of RE deployment.

In terms of international financial flows, the UNFCCC's Clean Development Mechanism (CDM) is particularly effective in countries facing high risk and incomplete financial markets. Interventions include credit provision, knowledge, and skills transfer and market signalling (Kim and Park, 2018). In individual country cases like Uganda and Senegal, market and regulatory reforms are conducted with the involvement of international financial actors to de-risk investments (Kruger and Eberhard, 2018). This leads to success in Senegal's RE penetration. However, questions loom on the loss of local agency over energy policy and the sovereign decision-making about matters related to the energy sector (van den Bold, 2022).

2.3.2. Transitioning away from coal

In the debate on transitioning away from fossil fuels, well-designed international agreements seem to have the potential to overcome certain political economy factors. For instance, the fossil fuel subsidy phase-out agreement at the 2009 Pittsburgh Summit demonstrates how transparency and oversight in non-binding international open club approaches can facilitate participation in global agreements (Aldy, 2017). Parallely, the national context is decisive for participation in international agreements, as the probability to join the Powering Past Coal Alliance (PPCA) increases with higher GDP per capita, transparent and independent governments and lower coal share in the electricity mix (Jewell et al., 2019).

Although we search for effective transitioning away from fossil fuel, including oil and gas, we only find effective national examples for coal. The effective policy examples for transitioning away from coal differ among each other regarding the political motivation, market structure and energy mix. We could identify three distinct entry point clusters (see Figure 9).

Figure 9: Entry points transitioning away from coal

The first cluster, **coal dependent & climate advocate**, consists of phase out pledges in Canada and Germany that both established an international standing as leading nations in their efforts to fight climate change. At the same time their coal represents a noticeable fraction in their energy mix which rises the challenge of stranded assets and structural change. Motivated by their proactive international standing and exposure to environmental impacts, such as air pollution and flooding, they established a stakeholder commission, and thus enhanced the required institutional capacity. Furthermore, health gain framing in climate policy is a central element for public support and strengthening of pro-policy coalitions (Millar et al., 2020). In Canada, a narrow mandate of the stakeholder commission contributes to specific and ambitious results in climate mitigation and public involvement (Gürtler et al., 2021). In contrary, the broader mandate of the German stakeholder commission slowed down ambition (Gürtler et al., 2021) but is recognized as key to ease lobby resistance accompanied by large compensation payments and removal of fossil fuel subsidies (Furnaro, 2023; Markard et al., 2021; Oei et al., 2020). The German case further illustrates that auctioning with a declining ceiling price is superior to pre-determined or negotiated compensations in terms of efficient retirements (Tiedemann and Müller-Hansen, 2023).

The case of the United Kingdom (UK) is rather unique as the coal share has been declining due to liberalized market, rise of renewables as well as substitutability with nuclear and gas (Brauers et al., 2020; Isoaho and Markard, 2020). In addition, no new coal-fired power plants were constructed in the UK during the 2000s and 2010s (Walk and Stognief, 2022). Therefore, vested interests and coal phase out oppositions were comparably weak and the case of the UK can be considered **liberalized and coal independent**. Furthermore, rising environmental concerns and supportive social activism combined with pressure from EU, as well as national climate policies, enabled the phase out pledge in 2019 (Isoaho and Markard, 2020).

Finally, the **financially supported** cluster consists of the coal phase out pledge in Vietnam. Do and Burke (2023) emphasize that the key factors enabling the coal phase-out commitment are the political motivation to secure international support for domestic green growth and the limited availability of financing for new coal power plants. Moreover, participating in international efforts to address climate change is a central political priority.

2.3.3. Zero emission vehicles

For the decarbonization of the transport sector, a broad policy mix consisting of demand, supply, and infrastructure support policies is deployed in all effective cases. Policy stringency and durability over years and decades also played a major role for sustained successful outcomes and a front-runner zero emission vehicle (ZEV) role.

We derive three distinct entry point clusters (see Figure 10). **Green innovators** have a particularly high share of EV sales and a relative large share of renewables in their electricity-mix (Dijk et al., 2020). They are motivated by emission reduction goals and partially by economic growth opportunities. For these cases, the transition is enabled by political economy factors, namely an absence of a strong conventional automotive industry in the region that could have opposed or delayed a new business model. In addition, the effective policy cases are marked by high financial capacity, with direct state investments in ZEV infrastructure (EV charging and refuelling stations as well as hydrogen production for fuel cell) serving as the central element of the policy mix. Further, non-financial incentives are mentioned to have a pivotal role, e.g., the privilege for EVs to use the bus line in Norway (Barton and Schütte, 2017; Dijk et al., 2020). The effective policy cases build on a history of several decades of ambitious and enduring ZEV policies (Trencher, 2020), which have culminated in stringent ZEV deployment policies, such as internal combustion engine vehicle (ICEV) sales bans or 100 percent EV sales targets (Lemphers et al., 2022). Moreover, support coalitions of environmental groups and state-led organizations are established in all cases and benefit from electrification policies of other industries (Lemphers et al., 2022; Trencher, 2020)

Figure 10: Entry points for Zero emission vehicles

The **state-led front-runner** China has the world's highest absolute EV sales. Stringent policies are enabled by the country's oil import dependency and severe energy security concerns considering the country's rising energy demand in the transport sector (Ma et al., 2019). High air pollution increased the urgency for a sectoral transition (Liu et al., 2020). As a planned economy China has experience in deploying state-led industrial policies and supporting demand, e.g., via state-owned enterprises (Gomes et al., 2023). Other than for the green innovators, China has an important conventional automotive industry which is a major motivation for the government to support EV deployment, recognizing an economic opportunity in becoming a leader in this emerging technology. Shao and Mišić (2023) show that the presence of conventional automotive industry is helpful for EV production and sales in some provinces, while hindering in others. In particular, those jurisdictions that opened their supply and demand-side policy support also to EVs from other jurisdictions and countries and allowed for inflow of foreign capital became effective EV hubs (e.g., Anhui province, Shanghai). Generally, provinces with relatively high GDP per capita were more effective in EV deployment than others.

The core policies implemented are similar to those of the green innovators, emphasizing direct infrastructure investments. However, as a state-led front-runner, China places a greater emphasis on subsidies and support for supply side R&D. Additionally, tailored non-financial demand-side incentives are also considered effective in several Chinese cities. For instance, in Shenzhen exempting EVs from mandatory and costly licence plate lotteries is recognized as particularly beneficial (Gomes et al., 2023).

Estonia, a **starter and niche tester**, still lags the leading countries in terms of the share of EVs in total car sales. However, Joller and Varblane (2016) find that Estonia has achieved an effective EV introduction phase from 2011 until 2014. Enabled by an extraordinary funding source (excess CO₂ quotas under the CDM), strong public acceptance and a renewable energy-based electricity supply. Policies in Estonia primarily focus on direct investments in infrastructure, R&D, and fiscal or financial demand-side policies. However, additional public funds are limited and the further policy strategy uncertain.

2.4. Discussion

The regional sample of this study predominantly focuses on China, Europe, and North America, reflecting central regions of high-impact climate policies⁶ in the Policy Database (NewClimate Institute et al., 2024). However, further regions with several high-impact policies in the Policy Database such as Argentina, Indonesia, Japan,

⁶ High impact policies are classified using different methods, including country experts and current policy GHG projections and latest insights from Nascimento et al. (2022) (CPB, 2023).

Thailand and Turkey are under-represented in this sample, indicating the need for more policy research within these areas.

Comparing the deployment of sample technologies, solar PV has shorter development times, lower investment risk and costs, and greater geographic and scale flexibility. In contrast, wind deployment requires a high level of labour intensity, which can be advantageous if policymakers aim to prioritize job creation and stimulate local economic growth. However, a challenge can be the requirement of higher levels of technical knowledge and expertise (Kim and Park, 2018). Both onshore solar and wind PV are intermittent energy sources, presenting a common challenge for grid integration and energy pricing, as their supply cannot flexibly be adjusted to meet fluctuations in market demand. This can lead to curtailment, which occurs when operational power plants are forced to shut down due to oversupply and other grid limitations (Do et al., 2020; Gao and Yuan, 2020; Kim, 2021). Offshore wind power offers the potential for greater stability in electricity generation by utilizing the regularity and intensity of offshore wind patterns. However, deployment of offshore wind comes at the expense of grid connectivity challenges, higher costs and project risk as well as a more complex regulatory environment (Cowell et al., 2017; O'Hanlon and Cummins 2020).

Despite successful deployment cases in advanced economies, significant challenges persist. Notably, large disparities exist between subregions, such as the differences observed between state and federal policies in the USA. (Narassimhan et al., 2022). Similarly, considerable differences exist across member state performance within the EU stemming from differences in public support as well as fossil fuel dependencies (Musiał et al., 2021). A key policy mechanism employed in advanced economies, FiTs face challenges related to cost-sustainability and competitive dynamics. For instance, the rate reduction around 2013 is linked to a slowdown of RE growth (Shivakumar et al., 2019). Concurrently, Southern Europe has been undergoing a transition towards more market-based instruments (Hadjipanayi et al., 2016).

For emerging and middle income economies, concerns about policy stability and consistency are paramount (Vakulchuk et al., 2023). Cases like China show remarkable speed and scale of RE deployments. However, these advancements raise challenges in policy coordination. In addition to electricity curtailment; managing conflicts among policy-induced interest groups presents another challenge. While interest groups can contribute to policy stability, they may also act as obstacles to necessary policy change and adjustment (Do et al., 2020; Gao and Yuan, 2020; Karltorp et al., 2017).

Countries like Brazil, India and South Africa adapt instruments to local objectives and capacities. Auctions are an effective way to achieve diverse requirements while

scaling across institutional contexts, capacities, and technologies. They show strategic state support without major financial strains, and different ways to tackle knowledge and skill gaps. However, challenges remain, in the scale of deployment and to meet energy security concerns as well as increasing energy demand.

While the involved parties agreed on a coal phase-out in Germany, it is expected that an earlier phase-out would have been cheaper, reduced environmental damage, and would have led to accelerated regional recovery (Oei et al., 2020). Further, Gürtler, Löw Beer, and Herberg (2021) point out that the overburdening mandate assigned to the German commission resulted in hesitant compromise. Specifically, the compensation schemes are criticized as the bilateral contracts lack of transparency and are too generous (Furnaro, 2023).

The abrupt transitioning away from coal and simultaneously scaling of renewables in Vietnam rise challenges to the electricity grid and concerns on power shortages (Do et al., 2020; Do and Burke, 2023). Therefore, the development of the electricity grid and storage capacity should belong to the central elements in climate policy strategies and international financial support.

Overall, we noticed that the speed of policy sequencing is an important factor. Countries that implemented a gradual transition seem to rely on more policy support than those that enacted abrupt, in a short notice transition (Brauers et al., 2020).

This review is subject to several limitations. First, the Policy Database indicates that some regions that effectively reduced emission with high-impact policies are not represented in our sample. Consequently, future climate policy research should prioritize the examination of best practice cases specially in East Asia and Latin America, as these can offer valuable insights for countries within comparable regional contexts. Second, the majority of extracted articles are case studies lacking statistical measures of causality or effect size for the policy instrument's impact on deployment. As a result, the observed deployment effect may be correlational, and the identified entry points could be idiosyncratic, potentially failing to produce comparable outcomes in another comparable region. This can be the case if unidentified variables within the study contributed to the success of the policy intervention, indicating the presence of omitted variable bias. Additionally, it may arise if distinct regions face additional barriers to policy adoption. Finally, this review is limited to the provision of an overview of possible entry points without quantifiable ranking criteria regarding effect size of deployment. Moreover, some studies assess the effectiveness of a policy intervention based on a limited timeframe, which may not accurately capture its most recent or long-term outcomes.

2.5. Conclusion and policy implications

In this systematic literature review, we collect combinations of policy instruments and enabling factors identified in the literature as contributors to the successful deployment of mitigation technologies or the transition away from fossil fuels. Through this review, we develop a taxonomy of technological entry points for deep decarbonization at the sector level.

Our review reveals an important research gap. Although in East Asia and South America, countries like Argentina, Indonesia, Japan, Thailand, and Turkey have implemented high-impact climate policies, they seem to be underrepresented in the literature on effective climate policies (especially qualitative case studies that provide explanatory insights on enabling factors).

The entry points we identify from the literature are sector and technology-specific, and within each sector and technology, strategies vary based on regional context. Therefore, we clustered the entry points to establish a classification of best practice policy groups and highlighting key enabling factors that can serve as role models or provide essential learnings. Overall, most of the enabling factors identified relate to economic feasibility, although institutional capacity, interest group support, and market structure appear with the highest frequency.

Regarding the deployment of renewables, six different clusters are identified. Three of them primarily capture advanced economies. The instrumentalists focus on market-based instruments to generate favourable conditions (like tax credits and credit market incentives) with reduced direct governmental intervention. In contrary, the strategists build on strong institutional capacity to incentivize distributed power producers. Within the cluster of regional autonomy, local authorities with a high degree of power and competencies effectively utilize their local engagement and influence.

Two clusters rather capture middle income and emerging economies. The planners rely on a medium to long term top down approach with a high degree of public involvement in the energy sector. In the cluster of adaptive pragmatism, regions adapt policy instruments to context-specific needs, whereby renewable deployment is rather considered additional capacity for rising energy demand and security concerns than as substitute for fossil energy.

Financial cross-cutters represent an intersectional cluster and refer to financial entry points where the focus relies on the provision of stable and risk reduced financing conditions, e.g., via a national development bank.

We identified three distinct pathways for transitioning away from coal. In the special case of a low coal energy share and available energy substitutes, national climate policies and rising environmental concerns can be sufficient to support a coal phase-out. However, the presence of high coal energy shares is likely to be accompanied by a strong opposition that requires an establishment of a stakeholder commission. Canada is a convincing example that a narrow mandate of the stakeholder commission can lead to more efficient and ambitious results. The German case illustrates that auctioning with a declining ceiling price can be an effective approach for retirement programs. Finally, for financially constrained or developing economies, international financial support for green growth can be a motivation for transitioning away from coal, as demonstrated by the best practice example of Vietnam.

Best practice examples for policy induced deployment of net-zero emission vehicles all rely on policy support for infrastructure development. We classify three distinct pathways. In the absence of conventional automotive industry, strong financial capacity and large renewable electricity share enable enduring policy support and stringed policies like ICEV sales ban. Strong centralized states with state-owned enterprises can see an economic growth opportunity and support the deployment by infrastructure investments, R&D and sales regulation. Finally, large funding resources can enable nice testers, like Estonia.

3. Taxonomy of entry-points related to behaviour changes

3.1. Background

Research on climate change mitigation has traditionally concentrated on supply side strategies, such as renewable energy supply and carbon capture and storage (CCS). In contrast, demand-side solutions have received less emphasis. These solutions focus on reducing energy use, alternative ways to meet service demands and adopting more sustainable technologies, including for example travelling less, adopting healthier diets, or opting for smaller living spaces. Recently, however, behaviour changes are becoming more acknowledged for their potential to reduce emissions (Akenji et al., 2021; Capstick et al., 2021; Costa et al., 2021; Grubler et al., 2018; IPCC, 2018; Ivanova et al., 2020; van Vuuren et al., 2018; Vita et al., 2019). This is also substantiated by the inclusion of a chapter dedicated to demand in both the IPCC WGIII reports and the UNEP Emissions Gap Report (Capstick et al., 2021; Creutzig et al., 2022).

Given the stringent emissions reductions needed to limit global warming to well below 2 °C, in line with the Paris Agreement, and the complexity of the systems involved, it is essential for effective policymaking to evaluate a broad range of emission reduction strategies, ensuring that both supply-side solutions and behaviour changes are considered. But still, behaviour and lifestyle are often underrepresented in long-term climate mitigation models like IAMs, which tend to focus on technological solutions (Saujot et al., 2020). Other modelling studies, in contrast, have extensively analysed lifestyle impacts. Studies based on consumption-based carbon footprint (CBCF) distinguish significant regional differences in per-capita emissions, lifestyles, and technology use and show how close different regions are to reaching reduction targets (Akenji et al., 2021; Brizga et al., 2017; Heinonen et al., 2020; Lettenmeier et al., 2019). This can help to understand the feasibility of behaviour changes in climate strategies.

Research on sustainable lifestyles spans qualitative and quantitative disciplines. Qualitative studies are primarily intent-oriented and explore the motivations behind lifestyle changes and provide insights into when, why, and how these changes occur; often focusing on enabling factors (Echegaray, 2021; Green and Vergragt, 2002; Manzini and Jegou, 2003; Mont et al., 2014; Quist et al., 2001; Quist and Leising, 2016; Schmidt-Scheele et al., 2022). They are usually applied in areas such as behavioural economics, environmental psychology, social practice theory, and innovation and socio-technical transition studies. On the other hand, quantitative studies are primarily impact-oriented and quantify the environmental effects of lifestyle changes. This often involves the use of models, such as life cycle assessments, consumption-based carbon accounting, agent-based modelling, and sometimes IAMs.

In this chapter, we present the findings from a comprehensive literature review conducted by van den Berg et al. (2023), providing insights into several key areas. The review delves into the terminology relevant to behaviour changes, offering a clear framework for understanding the various concepts involved. It identifies a range of entry points for implementing behaviour changes, along with the enabling factors that facilitate these shifts.

As part of task 3.2, we have compiled a spreadsheet providing an overview of entry points for behaviour change. This is available [here](#).

3.2. Frameworks and definitions

Having a common set of definitions is useful in a highly multidisciplinary field. Therefore, we begin by clarifying the distinction between behaviour changes, lifestyle changes, and consumption changes, as they are related but distinct concepts. Behaviour changes refer to specific actions or habits, while lifestyle changes encompass broader shifts in daily routines or values. Consumption changes can be considered as the outcomes of both behaviour and lifestyle changes.

From the perspective of a consumer, consumption can be categorized into four domains: food, residential (heating, cooling, and appliance use), transport, and the use of goods and services. Of course, changes in one domain can influence the others. For instance, shifts in leisure activities frequently impact consumption in multiple categories. According to van den Berg et al. (2023), specific changes within these domains are referred to as behaviour changes, while lifestyle change reflects a change in a consistent set of behaviours across domains. For example, a person who adopts a sustainable lifestyle by choosing to live in a car-free neighbourhood may primarily use public transportation, bike for short trips, and prefer to buy groceries from local farmers' markets. This lifestyle, therefore, has implications for behaviours across various domains.

Behaviour changes can also be categorized based on their impact on energy demand and resource use. A widely used approach to structure policy entry-points on behaviour change is the Avoid-Shift-Improve (ASI) framework (Creutzig et al., 2018).

- **Avoid** refers to changes that reduce unnecessary use of resources, like energy or food, especially in developed countries. In this context, "unnecessary" refers to consumption that is not essential for maintaining or enhancing the quality of the services offered.

- **Shift** refers to the use of alternative technologies and systems that are already widely available. Generally, these alternatives provide a (slightly) different type of service. For instance, this may include opting for cycling instead of driving or selecting plant-based alternatives in place of meat.
- **Improve** refers to the adoption of enhanced technologies that operate more efficiently.

The categorization is not always clear-cut. For example, transitioning from gas boilers with radiators to heat pumps using underfloor heating may be viewed as a shift to an alternative technology (shift) but can also be seen as a technological adaptation where user adoption is the primary behaviour change (improve). Likewise, adopting electric vehicles can be regarded as a straightforward technological replacement (improve) if the user has short commutes and adequate infrastructure, but if the infrastructure is lacking, adopting electric vehicles may require a lifestyle change (shift) as the nature of the service they provide differs.

Samadi et al. (2017) offer a complementary categorization, distinguishing measures based on efficiency, consistency (or technological substitution), and sufficiency (or lifestyle change). By broadening the concept of "consistency" beyond just technological substitution, the categories become:

- **Efficiency** refers to delivering the same output using fewer resources ("the input-output relation is improved"). For example, driving a more fuel-efficient car achieves the same travel distance with less energy.
- **Consistency** refers to substitution, where different inputs to provide the same service ("fundamental changes in production and consumption"). An example is switching from imported food to locally produced food: the service of providing nourishment remains the same, but the source of the food changes.
- **Sufficiency** involves lifestyle changes where the original service is replaced with an alternative (it "is linked to the level of demand for goods and services"). For example, instead of travelling long distances, people might choose to have vacations closer to home.

This framework aligns with the ASI framework: "improve" corresponds to efficiency and consistency, while "shift" and "avoid" align with lifestyle changes (sufficiency). Figure 11 illustrates how both frameworks can be employed to categorize examples of behaviour changes.

Figure 11: Categorization of behaviour changes. They can be categorized in different consumption domains and using the frameworks “avoid-shift-improve” by Creutzig et al. (2018) or “efficiency-consistency-sufficiency” by Samadi et al. (2017). Adopted from van den Berg et al. (2023).

Behaviour changes do not necessarily lead to (exclusively) positive environmental impacts. For example, while locally sourced food can reduce the carbon footprint from transportation, it might still have high water or land use requirements depending on the crop or production method. Within the context of identifying entry-points for deep emission reductions, van den Berg et al. (2019) provide a useful definition of lifestyle change that can be applied similarly to behaviour change:

Behaviour changes “are those that lead, or aim to lead, to the avoidance, shift, and in some cases, improvement in energy service demand, depending on the context and irrespective of their initial intent.”

3.3. Literature on behaviour change

Van den Berg et al. (2023) conducted a comprehensive review of the current literature to find entry-points on lifestyle changes and sustainable behaviours for reducing emissions. A broad and systematic search strategy was applied to identify and analyse relevant studies. The majority of studies focused on transport (62 papers),

residential energy use (59), and food and diet (33), while fewer examined consumer goods (4). An overview of the literature review process is depicted in Figure 12.

Figure 12: Selection procedure of the literature review. The numbers included are the number of articles that focus on the respective domains in the literature.

Effective understanding and assessment of entry points for behaviour change involves acknowledging its definitions across various disciplines, which emphasize different aspects of intent and impact. Akenji and Chen (2016) characterize sustainable lifestyles as habits or patterns of behaviour that minimize the use of natural resources and the generation of waste while maintaining a fair and decent living. In contrast, Samadi et al. (2017) characterise behaviour changes in scenario modelling as replacing one activity with a different but related service. These differing perspectives underscore the dual focus on motivation and outcomes of lifestyle changes, as noted by Gifford et al. (2011). In the next two sections, we describe the entry points from these two perspectives.

3.3.1. The impact-oriented approach

This section focuses on the impacts of lifestyle changes found in impact-oriented studies. To integrate the intent-oriented perspective, the 'avoid', 'shift', and 'improve' is used to assess how different behaviours contribute. Figure 13 shows an overview of behaviours categorized in the relevant domains.

Food

In the food domain, behavioural measures primarily centre around dietary changes, focusing on reduced meat-product consumption. This can be interpreted as either a *shift* or *avoid* depending on whether the emphasis is on intake of calories or meat itself. Other behaviour changes are also explored in the literature, such as reducing

food waste, classified as *avoid*, and opting for organic, local foods, which are categorized as *improve*.

Residential

The residential sector encompasses a wide variety of services, including cleaning, cooking, entertainment, heating and cooling, and shelter provision. This diversity creates opportunities for a range of behaviour changes that can help to reduce emissions. Most focus on *shift* and *avoid*, like adjustments in temperature setpoints, reduced water heating, managing waste, and reduced dwelling size. Focusing on *improve*, options for households include purchasing efficient appliances, and using smart appliances. Most residential measures are actually difficult to classify within the ASI categorization. For instance, using renewable mini-grids *improves* the carbon intensity of the energy source, but users may also need to *shift* their energy consumption patterns to different times to align with the variable output of the renewable sources (intermittency).

Transport

In transport, most of the measures modelled are *shifts* towards less intensive modes of transport, such as carpooling, cycling, walking, or using public transport to reach the same destination. Other measures like eco-driving and maintaining vehicles, which fall under the *improve* category, have also been modelled. In the transport domain, there is limited variety in behaviour changes classified as *avoid*. These changes would primarily focus on reducing travel demand and, depending on the context, may require highly transformative change.

Consumer goods and services

Consumer goods and services are explored less than the other domains. This is mainly because their indirect effects on energy reduction are harder to track and vary based on contextual factors (such as the production origin). Emissions occur not only during the production and disposal phases of a product's life but also in other domains. For instance, reduced washing or washing at lower temperatures (sustainable use of goods) increases lifespan of clothing, but also reduces energy demand for water heating.

Emissions can be reduced by *avoiding* the need of goods through reduced purchasing of goods and sharing products (e.g., car sharing). Additionally, digitalization of goods (e.g., digital newsletters instead of printed materials) and purchasing sustainable goods (e.g., designed for longer lifespans) could *improve* the amount of goods needed to achieve the same level of service or the amount of emissions associated with the production of those goods.

Cross-domain lifestyle changes

Two promising entry points among cross-domain lifestyle changes are time use shifts and transformative social change movements. Time use shifts can result in significant changes across various domains. For instance, reduced working hours may lead to a decreasing need for transport and more time for healthier cooking habits, but it could also increase the demand for residential heating and cooling. An important requirement for time shifts to be possible is that people need both sufficient resources and time to adopt these changes.

Transformative social change movements can mobilize collective action and advocate shifts in societal values, behaviours, and policies. They can complement other sustainable behaviours and have substantial consequences for the feasibility of achieving ambitious climate targets.

Figure 13: Behaviours categorized in the relevant domains (transport, residential, food, consumer goods & services). Their vertical position depends on how each behaviour can contribute to more sustainable living ("improve", "shift" or "avoid"). Colours indicate the research field(s) that studied these behaviours: EIO-LCA (Jones and Kammen, 2011), IO analysis (Bjelle et al., 2018), economic models (Geisendorf and Klippert, 2017; GLAMURS, 2016) and energy models (Girod et al., 2013; Grubler et al., 2018; Stehfest et al., 2009; van de Ven et al., 2018; van Sluisveld et al., 2016; van Vuuren et al., 2018). Adopted from van den Berg et al.(2023).

3.3.2. The intent-oriented approach: enablers

Intent-oriented literature focuses on the enabling factors and barriers affecting behaviour change. This more qualitative approach can help identify promising methodologies. Behaviour is heavily influenced by contextual factors such as access to resources, cultural norms, economic conditions, and infrastructure availability. Akenji and Chen (2016) introduced a framework that categorizes these factors into three determinants: “attitude”, “facilitators”, and “infrastructure”. Together, these determinants shape the context in which behaviour change occurs. They can influence behaviour both directly, through factors like personal attitudes, or indirectly, for example, by reducing infrastructural barriers.

The broader context and behaviour cannot be considered separately, because system and behaviour change are intrinsically connected (Capstick et al., 2021). When considered separately, this can give rise to ‘consumer scapegoatism’ (Akenji, 2014), where the responsibility for behaviour change is (unfairly) placed on consumers, even though many factors are outside their control. In this section we explore the three determinants that shape the context (Figure 14) in more detail.

Attitude		Facilitators		Infrastructure	
Cultures & social norms		Institutions, regulations & policies	Market conditions & prices	Physical infrastructure	Technology
Social interactions	Awareness & know-how	Education	Media	Product & architecture design	
		Income & wealth			
Subjective well-being	Psychology & personality	Costs	Nudges	Suitability & appropriateness	Options & alternatives
Personal norms		Cognitive & physical abilities		Convenience, availability & accessibility	

Figure 14: Theoretical framework of lifestyles (Akenji and Chen, 2016). Adopted from van den Berg et al. (2023).

Attitude

Attitude includes the norms, beliefs and feelings that influence a person’s decision-making. It is influenced by various factors, including awareness, cultures, norms and values, personality, social interactions, and well-being (both physical and

psychological). Our environmental identity is affected by it. This also impacts how aware we are of the consequences of our actions. The literature emphasizes that this awareness is a key factor influencing behaviour (Neuvonen et al., 2014).

Recognizing individuality, including personal norms and societal identities, is important. People have unique characteristics, which influence their profiles and life stage – such as being conscious or enthusiastic, or a teenager or student (Geisendorf and Klippert, 2017; Li, 2017; van de Ven et al., 2018; Vergragt et al., 2016), but also how likely or quickly they adopt new behaviours, as outlined in the diffusion of innovations theory by Rogers (2003).

Research indicates that individuals often express support for pro-environmental values, but do not act accordingly (Ajzen, 1991; Babutsidze and Chai, 2018; Truelove and Parks, 2012). There is a difference between “compliance”, where people show pro-environmental behaviour only when being watched or evaluated, and “conversion”, where people sustain those behaviours on their own (Dolan et al., 2010). Improved self-efficacy can help to bridge this so called value-action gap by making people feel more confident in their ability to take action (Cornelius et al., 2014). Some researchers believe that reflecting on their behaviours can help maintaining a lasting change (Morris et al., 2012; Petty and Cacioppo, 1986). However, higher awareness or belief is generally not enough and bridging the value-action gap may require collective action and stronger social norms (Dolan et al., 2010; Löschel et al., 2017; Obradovich and Guenther, 2016; Wang, 2018).

In addition, research highlights the importance of well-being in adopting sustainable behaviours. When consumers recognize the co-benefits of sustainable practices, particularly those related explicitly to well-being rather than economic benefits, they are more likely to embrace them (van de Ven et al., 2018). Understanding and integrating these co-benefits is therefore important for promoting behaviour change (Quam et al., 2017; van de Ven et al., 2018).

Facilitators

Facilitators are “a set of factors that contribute to the possibility for certain behaviour patterns or a lifestyle to actualize” (Akenji and Chen, 2016). These include public policy, pricing, and nudge techniques: they facilitate sustainable lifestyle changes. Facilitators are relevant for policymakers as they can be shaped by institutions, markets, education, and media. They play a crucial role in determining how likely sustainable behaviours are to be adopted. For example, subsidies, taxes, and deposit-refunds influence consumer decision-making by altering prices (Akenji et al., 2012; Dubois and Ceron, 2015; GLAMURS, 2016; Hanley and Brennan, 2012; Moreau et al., 2017; Webb, 2012). Facilitators can also influence other factors that impact sustainable behaviour choices, such as employment and income.

To quantify the willingness to adopt sustainable practices, researchers often use the concept of Willingness To Pay (WTP) (von Borgstede et al., 2013). This refers to the extra costs that individuals are willing to accept for environmentally friendly behaviours. However, this approach is being challenged by critiques of rational choice theory, which focuses on cost-based decision-making. Fields like behavioural economics, psychology, and welfare theory propose alternative approaches. One prominent example is nudging (Thaler and Sunstein, 2008). Nudges aim to subtly guide people's choices without imposing strict financial or regulatory measures, which are often seen as restrictive and limiting the freedom of choice (Backhaus et al., 2012). Examples of nudging-related mitigation strategies are *default-setting and labels* (Girod et al., 2014) and the use of *five levers of change* (Unilever, 2013). However, nudges alone may not be sufficient and a combination with other methods might be necessary to achieve the desired results (Thaler and Sunstein, 2008).

Infrastructure

Infrastructure refers to "socio-ecological interfaces that support consumption activities" (Akenji and Chen, 2016). Infrastructure is needed because it is difficult for consumers to express demand for products or services that are not available (Akenji et al., 2012). For example, public transport systems are crucial if people want to reduce their reliance on personal vehicles. Similarly, reliable internet and well-equipped home office setups are essential for facilitating remote working.

Infrastructure encompasses more than just physical infrastructure and technology. It also involves thoughtful design of products and architectural features that can facilitate desired behaviours, for instance through safe road design with separated bike lanes. Innovative solutions can promote alternative, more sustainable behaviours. Behavioural theorists highlight the influence of technology on behaviour (Morris et al., 2012) and that the accessibility, availability and convenience of infrastructure are particularly important factors that can encourage sustainable behaviour (Lin, 2013).

While new designs can promote positive changes, they also come with the risk of potential lock-ins that limit consumer choices. A prime example is the car-centric urban planning in many existing cities that limits space for alternative transportation modes. A "smaller city block" system that allows pedestrians to change direction easily, could be beneficial (Creutzig et al., 2016). But such changes cannot always be straightforwardly implemented in existing neighbourhoods. This highlights the need for careful consideration about infrastructural development.

Another aspect of infrastructure, though less technical, is the role of public spaces, buildings, and urban infrastructure. When designed cleverly, they can foster co-creation and participation in neighbourhoods (Backhaus et al., 2012). This type of bottom-up infrastructure, together with local partnerships and beneficial settlement

patterns, can stimulate collective action by encouraging community engagement and collaboration.

3.4. Scenarios in Integrated Assessment Models

Considering the significant uncertainty and complexity associated with climate mitigation strategies, scenario planning can be a useful method for making flexible long-term plans and decisions (Amer et al., 2013; Volkery and Ribeiro, 2009). Scenarios help to imagine possible futures and to understand their implications for decision-making. One way to apply scenario planning is via model-based scenario development. Capturing lifestyle and behaviour change in scenarios is difficult due to their complex dependency on economic, psychological, and demographic variables that vary across social and geographical levels (Saujot et al., 2020). When incorporated into modelled scenarios, it is often through stylized assumptions (Anable et al., 2012; Faber et al., 2012; Grubler et al., 2018; Röös et al., 2017; Stehfest et al., 2009; van de Ven et al., 2018; van Sluisveld et al., 2016; van Vuuren et al., 2018). Only a few global modelling studies explicitly explore the potential role of behaviour measures as mitigation options (van den Berg et al., 2021).

Exploring lifestyle changes in Integrated Assessment Models (IAMs) is important for multiple reasons (Saujot et al., 2020). First, it provides policy-makers with quantitative knowledge about the impacts of lifestyle changes allowing for informed decision-making. Second, the scenarios can be used for dialogue and support citizen and stakeholder engagement through participatory approaches. Lastly, it allows for a holistic framing of the problems and solutions related to lifestyle.

Grubler et al. (2018) showed that incorporating lifestyle changes into their “low energy demand” (LED) scenario can lead to transformative emission reductions. However, the outcomes lack qualitative insights and rely on external assumptions. Also other scenario studies show that behaviour changes can significantly reduce emissions (Lettenmeier et al., 2019; van de Ven et al., 2018; van Sluisveld et al., 2016; van Vuuren et al., 2018). Furthermore, by comparing regional modelling outputs and relating them to the regional contexts, van der Berg et al. (2021) showed that lessons can be learned from existing examples, such as in Japan, where enhancing infrastructure, technology, and electrification has facilitated lower emissions. However, to achieve a better representation of lifestyle change in scenarios, further improvements in IAMs are necessary (van den Berg, 2023). This could be accomplished by incorporating more consumer heterogeneity or by using endogenous lifestyle modules, which could lead to new insights for future scenarios.

3.4.1. SLIM scenarios

As a first step to incorporate lifestyle change better into IAMs, van den Berg et al. (2023) designed the SLIM (Sustainable Living In Modeling) scenario narratives. They

explicitly clarify the role of society, enablers, lifestyles and behaviours in driving system change. The scenarios use four distinct “worlds” with contrasting perspectives: Designed World (sustainable lifestyles by default); Global Commons (an inclusive global governance system); Big Village (community-based sustainable living); and Pocket Lifestyles (peer-to-peer lifestyle platforms). The scenario creation involved workshops, document reviews and meetings with people from different disciplines with expertise in qualitative scenario development, sustainable lifestyles, modelling, and policy. Ultimately, two of these scenarios were also integrated into the IMAGE model (van den Berg et al., 2024).

The scenarios differentiate between *individualistic vs collective values* and *centralized vs distributed access to structural support*. The first distinction considers whether changes in sustainable behaviour stem from individual decisions and individualistic values or emerge from a broader societal shift towards inclusivity and communal values. The second distinction considers access to structural support, whether it is centralised or distributed. Societal support is essential for sustainable lifestyles (Mont et al., 2014) and influences aspects such as infrastructure, legislation, government programs, and availability of local initiatives.

The SLIM scenarios also take social equity as a key consideration into their scenarios. A just transition should be part of the lifestyle change discussion to ensure that all communities are meaningfully involved. A common critique of lifestyle scenarios is that they show significant emission reductions from lifestyle change in the Global South, while there is still ample room for improvements in high-emitting regions. On the other hand, this could also be interpreted as leapfrogging rather than limiting economic development, avoiding costly investments in inefficient infrastructure. Nonetheless, such an approach can be viewed as unjust, as it assigns a large share of mitigation to regions with lower emission lifestyles than those in developed countries.

3.5. Final considerations

Behaviour and lifestyle changes do not emerge on their own. They depend on enabling factors, which can broadly be categorized into attitudes, facilitators, and infrastructure. Achieving sustainable lifestyle changes requires facilitation by policy to enable larger systems change that create favourable enabling conditions. This can ultimately reduce energy demand and resource use avoiding, shifting, or improving activities. Both centralized support and bottom-up initiatives can play a role in this process.

Behaviour and lifestyle changes must be considered as part of a larger system. Often, the responsibility for adopting sustainable behaviour is placed on consumers themselves (‘consumer scapegoatism’), overlooking the fact that many enabling conditions are beyond their control. Therefore, a comprehensive mitigation strategy

that takes the broader system into account is needed. This would help create the necessary conditions that enable behaviour and lifestyle changes. Moreover, the multidisciplinary nature of behaviour change calls for an integrated approach. As discussed, scenarios could provide a valuable framework for exploring how policies can shape these conditions and facilitate dialogue.

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Online Appendix

Abstract

This Online Appendix provides additional information about the manuscript and consists of the following online appendices:

Online Appendix A: Research selection

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Online Appendix A: Research selection

Table OA 1: SPIDER framework

Note: Table OA 1 reports the structuring of selected research using the SPIDER framework following Cook et al. (2012). This framework ensures a theoretically grounded derivation of central search terms as well as in- and exclusion criteria.

Sample	Phenomenon of Interest (Entry point)	Design	Evaluation	Research type
<i>The sample covers research on sectoral climate change mitigation policies. Therefore, it should include terms for policy and relevant sectors or specific technologies within the selected sectors.</i>	<i>To explore the how and why of sectoral climate change mitigation policies, the selected research is required to provide contextual assessments.</i>	<i>Selected research should provide an assessment of conducted policy cases and therefore rely on an observational design.</i>	<i>The outcome measure should be positive for mitigation technologies and negative for fossil fuels.</i>	<i>In order to conduct a comprehensive overview, we allow multiple methods.</i>
<p>Policies: <i>General:</i> policy <i>Specific:</i> Just Energy Transition Partnership, Climate Clubs, Carbon Clubs, International Transfers, International Cooperation, International Treaty, Climate Treaty, Climate Agreements Sectors: energy, transport, buildings, industry, carbon management Technologies <i>Mitigation technologies:</i> renewables, solar, wind, hydro, biomass, nuclear, geothermal, battery storage, hydrogen, methanol, ammonia, biochar, electro fuel, biofuel, bioenergy, biodiesel, ethanol, biomethane, synthetic fuel, electric arc furnace, heat pump, electrode boiler, electric vehicle, fuel cell, energetic refurbishment, energetic rehabilitation, energy renovation <i>Fossil fuel technologies:</i> coal, oil, gas</p> <p>In- and exclusion criteria Study analyses technologies in one or more of the following focus sectors of this review: energy, transport, industry, buildings or carbon management.</p>	<p>In- and exclusion criteria Study includes context specific enablers for the policy intervention or context specific barriers that the policy intervention is based on.</p>	<p>In- and exclusion criteria Study uses an empirical ex-post evaluation method (Qualitative or Quantitative).</p>	<p>Mitigation technologies : increase in deployment, best practice policy Fossil fuel technologies : decrease of deployment, best practice policy In- and exclusion criteria Study includes an effective climate policy with regard to technology deployment or phase-out.</p>	<p>In- and exclusion criteria Study is not a single method literature review.</p>

Table OA 2: Search string

Note: Table OA 2 reports the search string for the data bases Web of Science and Scopus including the number of resulting articles and date of the search.

Search string	Date	Resu lts
<p>TS=(("polic*" OR "Just?Energy?Transition?Partners hip*" OR "Climate\$Clubs" OR "Carbon\$Clubs" OR ("international*" NEAR/3 "transfer\$") OR ("international*" NEAR/3 "cooperation\$") OR "International Treat*" OR "Climate Treat*" OR "Climate\$Agreement*") AND (((("energy" OR "transport*" OR "building*" OR "industr*" OR "sector*") AND ("climat*" OR "net\$zero" OR "low\$carbon" OR "emission*" OR "CO2*" OR "GHG*" OR "greenhouse\$gas*" OR "decarboni?ation*") AND (("best" OR "good" OR "success*" OR "effective" OR "efficient") NEAR/5 ("polic*" OR "regulation\$") OR (("best?practice") NEAR/10 ("polic*" OR "regulation\$"))) OR (((("mitigation" OR "emission* reduction*" OR "net\$zero" OR "low* carbon") NEAR/5 ("technolog*" or "option*")) OR (("renewable*" OR "solar" OR "wind" OR "hydro" OR "biomass" OR "nuclear" OR "geotherm*" OR "solar\$thermal" OR "batter*" or "storage" OR "recycling" OR "hydrogen" OR "H2" OR "methanol" OR "ammonia" OR "methanol?to?olefins" OR " power?to?liquid" OR " power?to?gas" OR "CCS" OR "CCU" OR "DAC*" OR "BECCS" OR "biochar" OR "e-fuel*" OR "electrofuel*" OR "biofuel*" OR "bioenergy" OR "biodiesel" OR "ethanol*" OR "biomethane" OR "syn\$fuel*" OR "synthetic\$fuel*" OR "electric?arc?furnace" OR "eaf" OR "heat\$pump*" OR "electrode\$boiler*" OR "electric\$vehicle*" OR "EV" OR "fuel\$cell*")) NEAR/5 ("deployment" OR "rollout" OR "scaling*" OR</p>	<p>16.08.20 23</p>	<p>8265</p>

<p>"scale\$up" OR "scalab*" OR "usage" OR "expansion" OR (("best" OR "good" OR "success*" OR "effective" OR "efficient") NEAR/5 ("polic*" OR "regulation\$")) OR (("best?practice") NEAR/10 ("polic*" OR "regulation\$")))) OR (("district\$heat*" OR "grid*" OR "heat* network*") NEAR/5 ("expan*" OR "exten*" OR ("best" OR "good" OR "success*" OR "effective" OR "efficient") NEAR/5 ("polic*" OR "regulation\$")) OR (("best?practice") NEAR/10 ("polic*" OR "regulation\$")))) OR ("energetic refurbishment*" OR "energetic renovation*" OR "energetic rehabilitation*" OR "energy rehabilitation*" OR "energy renovation*") OR (("fossil*" OR "coal" OR "oil" or "gas") NEAR/5 ("phase* out*" OR "phase* down*" OR ("best" OR "good" OR "success*" OR "effective" OR "efficient") NEAR/5 ("polic*" OR "regulation\$")) OR (("best?practice") NEAR/10 ("polic*" OR "regulation\$"))))) NOT ("water" OR "*forest*" OR "farm*" OR "food*" OR "agric*" OR "agro*" OR "land* use" OR "LULUCF" OR "AFOLU"))</p>		
<p>Web of science additional filter: Articles, Review Articles, Early Access, English</p>	<p>16.08.20 23</p>	<p>7942</p>
<p>TITLE-ABS-KEY (("polic*" OR "Just Energy Transition Partnership*" OR "Climate Clubs" OR "Carbon Clubs" OR ("international*" W/3 "transfer ") OR ("international*" W/3 "cooperation ") OR "International Treat*" OR "Climate Treat*" OR "Climate Agreement*") AND (((("energy" OR "transport*" OR "building*" OR "industr*" OR "sector*") AND ("climat*" OR "net zero" OR "low carbon" OR "emission*" OR "CO2*" OR "GHG*" OR "greenhouse gas*" OR "decarboni ation*") AND ("best" OR "good" OR "success*" OR "effective" OR "efficient") W/5 ("polic*" OR "regulation ") OR</p>	<p>16.08.20 23</p>	<p>1042 6</p>

(("best practice") W/10 ("polic*" OR "regulation "))

OR (((("mitigation" OR "emission* reduction*" OR "net zero" OR "low* carbon") W/5 ("technolog*" or "option*")) OR

(("renewable*" OR "solar" OR "wind" OR "hydro" OR "biomass" OR "nuclear" OR "geotherm*" OR "solar thermal" OR "batter*" or "storage" OR "recycling" OR "hydrogen" OR "H2" OR "methanol" OR "ammonia" OR "methanol to olefins" OR "power to liquid" OR "power to gas" OR "CCS" OR "CCU" OR "DAC*" OR "BECCS" OR "biochar" OR "e-fuel*" OR "electrofuel*" OR "biofuel*" OR "bioenergy" OR "biodiesel" OR "ethanol*" OR "biomethane" OR "syn fuel*" OR "synthetic fuel*" OR "electric arc furnace" OR "eaf" OR "heat pump*" OR "electrode boiler*" OR "electric vehicle*" OR "EV" OR "fuel cell*"))

W/5 ("deployment" OR "rollout" OR "scaling*" OR "scale up" OR "scalab*" OR "usage" OR "expansion" OR ("best" OR "good" OR "success*" OR "effective" OR "efficient") W/5 ("polic*" OR "regulation ")) OR ((("best practice") W/10 ("polic*" OR "regulation "))

)) OR (("district heat*" OR "grid*" OR "heat* network*") W/5 ("expan*" OR "exten*" OR ("best" OR "good" OR "success*" OR "effective" OR "efficient") W/5 ("polic*" OR "regulation ")) OR ((("best practice") W/10 ("polic*" OR "regulation "))

))

OR ("energetic refurbishment*" OR "energetic renovation*" OR "energetic rehabilitation*" OR "energy rehabilitation*" OR "energy renovation*")

OR (("fossil*" OR "coal" OR "oil" or "gas") W/5 ("phase* out*" OR "phase* down*" OR ("best" OR "good" OR "success*" OR "effective" OR "efficient") W/5 ("polic*" OR "regulation ")) OR ((("best practice") W/10 ("polic*" OR "regulation "))

)))AND NOT ("water" OR "*forest*" OR "farm*" OR

<i>“food*” OR “agric*” OR “agro*” OR “land* use” OR “LULUCF” OR “AFOLU”))</i>		
<i>SCOPUS additional filter: Articles, reviews, English</i>	<i>16.08.20 23</i>	<i>7505</i>

Online Appendix B: Article screening

Figure OB 1: Quasi- sampling

Note. Figure OB 1 plots the evaluation of the quasi-sampling developed by Callaghan and Müller-Hansen (2020). Overall, the sample consists of 7,997 unique documents of which 2,924 are manually screened and 5,073 are automatically excluded. Therefore, the screening algorithm saved almost two thirds of work compared to a purely manual screening process. The open-source calculator Biased Urns for efficient Stopping Criteria in technology-Assisted Reviews can be used to validate the results (<https://mcallaghan.github.io/buscar-app/>).

a)

b)

Table OB 1: Overview of selected articles

<i>Reference</i>		<i>Method</i>	<i>Policy region</i>	<i>Sector</i>	<i>Technology</i>
<i>(Aldy 2015)</i>	1	Case study	G20	Energy	Coal
<i>(Amankwah-Amoah and Sarpong 2016)</i>	2	Case study	Ghana	Energy	Solar
<i>(Ameli, Pisu, and Kammen 2017)</i>	3	Regression analysis	California	Energy	Solar
<i>(Andrews-Speed 2015)</i>	4	Case study	UK, China	Energy	Solar, Wind
<i>(Azhgaliyeva et al.,2018)</i>	5	Regression analysis	Global	Energy	Wind
<i>(Banja et al.,2019)</i>	6	Case study	EU	Energy, Transport	Biofuel
<i>(Barton and Schütte 2017)</i>	7	Case study	Norway	Transport	BEV
<i>(Bourdais Park and Chung 2022)</i>	8	Case study	China	Energy	nuclear
<i>(Bradshaw and de Martino Jannuzzi 2019)</i>	9	Case study	Brazil	Energy	Solar, Wind
<i>(Brauers, Oei, and Walk 2020)</i>	10	Case study	Germany, UK	Energy	Coal
<i>(Chen et al.,2022)</i>	11	Regression analysis	Asia–Pacific	Energy	Renewables
<i>(Costa et al.,2022)</i>	12	Case study	Brazil	Energy	Solar, Wind
<i>(Cowell et al.,2017)</i>	13	Case study	UK	Energy	Wind, Solar
<i>(Crago and Chernyakhovskiy 2017)</i>	14	Regression analysis	US	Energy	Solar
<i>(Cross et al.,2021)</i>	15	Mixed methods	UK, Finland, Sweden, Denmark	Energy, Buildings	Biofuel
<i>(De Laurentis and Pearson 2021)</i>	16	Case study	Apulia, Tuscany, Scotland	Energy	Solar, Wind
<i>(Dent 2015)</i>	17	Case study	China	Energy	Solar, Wind, Renewables
<i>(Dijk et al.,2020)</i>	18	Case study	Norway	Transport	BEV
<i>(Thang Nam Do and Burke 2023)</i>	19	Case study	Vietnam	Energy	Coal
<i>(T. N. Do et al.,2021)</i>	20	Case study	Vietnam	Energy	Solar
<i>(T. N. Do et al.,2020)</i>	21	Survey	Vietnam	Energy	Solar
<i>(Ebadian et al.,2020)</i>	22	Case study	US, Brazil, Germany, Canada	Transport	Biofuel
<i>(Eberhard and Kåberger 2016)</i>	23	Case study	South Africa	Energy	Renewables
<i>(Flores-Fernández 2020)</i>	24	Case study	Chile	Energy	Wind, Solar

<i>(Furnaro 2023)</i>	25	Case study	Germany	Energy	Coal
<i>(Gaffney, Deane, and Gallachóir 2017)</i>	26	Mixed methods	Ireland	Energy	Wind
<i>(Gao and Yuan 2020)</i>	27	Case study	China	Energy	Solar
<i>(Garcia Padron 2016)</i>	28	Case study	Sweden	Energy	Renewables
<i>(Geddes, Schmidt, and Steffen 2018)</i>	29	Case study	UK, Germany	Energy	Solar, Wind
<i>(Giest 2015)</i>	30	Case study	Sweden	Energy	Wind
<i>(Gomes, Pauls, and ten Brink 2023)</i>	31	Case study	China, Shenzhen	Transport	BEV
<i>(Guild 2019)</i>	32	Case study	Philippines	Energy	Wind, Solar, Hydro-Electricity, Biomass
<i>(Guliyev 2023)</i>	33	Case study	Kazakhstan	Energy	Solar, Wind, Hydro-Electricity
<i>(Guertler, Beer, and Herberg 2021)</i>	34	Case study	Germany, Canada	Energy	Coal
<i>(Gustafsson and Anderberg 2022)</i>	35	Case study	Germany, France, Sweden	Energy	Biofuel
<i>(Hafeznia et al.,2017)</i>	36	Regression analysis	Iran	Energy	Solar
<i>(Hsu 2018)</i>	37	Case study	California	Energy	Solar
<i>(Inderberg and Wettestad 2015)</i>	38	Case study	UK	Carbon management	CCS
<i>(Isah et al.,2023)</i>	39	Case study	Brazil	Energy	Solar, Wind
<i>(Isoaho and Markard 2020)</i>	40	Regression analysis	UK	Energy	Coal
<i>(Jewell et al.,2019)</i>	41	Case study	France, Ireland, UK, Sweden, Mexico, Belgium, Austria, Italy, Ireland, Canada, Denmark, Finland, Netherlands, New Zealand, Portugal, Israel	Energy	Coal
<i>(Johansson 2021)</i>	42	Case study	Sweden	Buildings	Heat pumps
<i>(Joller and Varblane 2016)</i>	43	Mixed methods	Estonia	Transport	BEV
<i>(Kammermann 2018)</i>	44	Case study	Swiss	Energy	Hydroelectricity
<i>(Karltorp, Guo, and Sandén 2017)</i>	45	Case study	China	Energy	Wind

<i>(Kedron 2015)</i>	46	Regression analysis	Canada	Transport	Liquid Biofuels
<i>(J. Kim and Park 2018)</i>	47	Case study	Annex 2	Energy	Hydro-Electricity, Solar, Wind, Biomass
<i>(S. Kim et al.,2018)</i>	48	Case study	Korea	Energy, Buildings	Renewables, Grid
<i>(C. Kim 2021)</i>	49	Case study	Korea	Energy, Buildings	Solar, Wind
<i>(Kruger and Eberhard 2018)</i>	50	Case study	South Africa, Uganda	Energy	Solar
<i>(Lemphers et al.,2022)</i>	51	Case study	California, Norway, Québec	Transport	BEV
<i>(M. Liu et al.,2022)</i>	52	Case study	Germany, China	Buildings	Passive house
<i>(Z. Liu et al.,2019)</i>	53	Regression analysis	China	Buildings	Passive house
<i>(X. Liu et al.,2020)</i>	54	Case study	China	Transport	BEV
	55	Other Quantitative	China	Energy	Solid Biofuels, Gasous Biofuels
<i>(L. Liu, Li, and Xie 2017)</i>	56	Case study	China	Transport	BEV
<i>(Ma et al.,2019)</i>	57	Case study	Germany	Energy	Coal
<i>(Markard, Rinscheid, and Widdel 2021)</i>	58	Case study	South Africa, Mexico	Energy	Coal
<i>(Matsuo and Schmidt 2019)</i>	59	Case study	Ontario	Energy	Coal
<i>(Millar et al.,2020)</i>	60	Case study	US	Energy	Solar
<i>(Mirzania, Balta-Ozkan, and Marais 2020)</i>	61	Case study	Germany	Energy	Coal
<i>(Oei, Brauers, and Herpich 2020)</i>	62	Regression analysis	British Isles	Energy	Wind
<i>(O'Hanlon and Cummins 2020)</i>	63	Case study	US	Energy	Solar
<i>(Peña, Azevedo, and Marcelino Ferreira 2017)</i>	64	Case study	Portugal	Energy	Wind
<i>(Rechsteiner 2021)</i>	65	Case study	Germany	Energy	Solar, Wind, Renewables
<i>(Roppongi, Suwa, and De Oliveira 2017)</i>	66	Case study	Tokyo	Buildings	Refurbishment
<i>(Schmieder et al.,2023)</i>	67	Case study	Germany	Energy	Wind, Solar
<i>(Shao and Mišić 2023)</i>	68	Case study	Anhui Province, Jiangxi Province, Shanghai	Transport	BEV

<i>(Shidore and Busby)</i>	70	Regression analysis	India	Energy	Solar
<i>(Shrimali, Lynes, and Indvik 2015)</i>	71	Case study	US	Energy	Wind
<i>(Shuai and Rauffer 2021)</i>	72	Case study	California	Grid storage	Behind-the-meter (BTM) Energy storage
<i>(Sreenath et al.,2022)</i>	73	Case study	ASEAN	Energy	Solar
<i>(Strunz, Gawel, and Lehmann 2016)</i>	74	Regression analysis	Germany	Energy	Renewables
<i>(Thapar, Sharma, and Verma 2018)</i>	75	Mixed methods	India	Energy	Solar
<i>(Tiedemann and Müller-Hansen 2023)</i>	76	Case study	Germany	Energy	Coal
<i>(Trencher 2020)</i>	77	Case study	California	Transport	FCEV
<i>(Trotta, Spangenberg, and Lorek 2018)</i>	78	Case study	UK	Buildings	Refurbishment
<i>(van den Bold 2022)</i>	79	Case study	Senegal	Energy	Solar, Wind
<i>(Walk and Stognief 2022)</i>	80	Case study	UK	Energy	Coal
<i>(Wettestad, Inderberg, and Gulbrandsen 2023)</i>	81	Other Quantitative	Norway	Carbon management	CCS
<i>(Wurster and Hagemann 2020)</i>	82	Case study	Germany, Austria	Energy	Renewables
<i>(Wurster and Hagemann 2018)</i>	83	Regression analysis	Germany	Energy	Renewables
<i>(Xie, Zhou, and Hui 2022)</i>	84	Case study	China	Energy	Coal , Hydro-Electricity
<i>(Ydersbond and Korsnes 2016)</i>	85	Regression analysis	EU, China	Energy	Wind
<i>(A. H. Zhang et al.,2022)</i>	86	Case study	China	Energy	Solar
<i>(F. Zhang 2023)</i>	87	Case study	US, Germany, China	Energy	Solar
<i>(F. Zhang 2020)</i>	88	Regression analysis	China, Germany	Energy	Solar, Wind
<i>(Zhao et al.,2016)</i>	89	Regression analysis	China	Energy	Wind
<i>(Zhou and Solomon 2020)</i>	90	Case study	US	Energy	Renewables

Figure OB 2: Frequency of methodologies

Online Appendix C: Robustness check

Robustness checks for large clusters

Our random forest classifier was trained to predict the clusters; the final model shows very good performance. Accuracy measures the overall correctness of both positive and negative clusters among all predictions. Precision tests the proportion of positives which were correct. Recall tests the number of predictions belonging to a cluster the model got correct. F1 Score is the harmonic mean between precision and recall. Last ROG AUC tests the model's ability to distinguish between classes. Across the renewables clusters we see the model performing very well. In Transport we relatively weaker performance, this is due to the smaller size of each cluster and the overall dataset.

Table OC 1: Random forest classification performance – renewables

Cluster	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1 Score	ROC AUC
Adaptive_Pragmatists	0.963	0.936	1	0.966	0.999
Centralized_Industrial_Policy	0.842	0.794	0.933	0.856	0.949
Distributed_Industrial_Policy	0.894	0.887	0.91	0.895	0.968
Financial_Cross-Cutters	0.919	0.884	0.986	0.93	0.986
Market_Based	0.951	0.934	0.972	0.952	0.992
Regional_Autonomy	0.944	0.914	0.986	0.948	0.984
Mean	0.919	0.892	0.965	0.924	0.98

Note: This table presents the performance metrics of Random Forest classifiers for each renewable energy policy cluster. All metrics are calculated using 5-fold cross-validation with SMOTE oversampling to address class imbalance. The classifier uses balanced class weights to further mitigate imbalance effects.

Online Appendix D: Further sectors and technologies

Figure OD. 1 Bioenergy

Within the Bioenergy sector we could distinguish effective policy cases related to biomass as well as biofuel into two clusters. For the **biomass-rich nations** their substantial biomass resource is the primary motivation and enabling factor. The cases, including USA, Brazil Canada and China, rely on an abundant agricultural sector, extensive forest resources, or both, positioning them as natural leaders in bioenergy production. Additional motivation stems from energy security concerns and rural development goals (Ebadian et al., 2020; Liu et al., 2017), supported by a long-standing history of bioenergy policy strategy and ambitious climate targets (Kedron, 2015). The central policy instruments include biofuel blending mandate (as applied in USA, Brazil and Canada), supply-side tax credits as well as grants and targeted financial instruments to encourage the production of advanced biofuel (e.g., credit policies and equity participation (Ebadian et al., 2020)).

For the second cluster, the **Policy-Driven Leaders**, the primary focus is on strong, well-established policy frameworks, with bioenergy and biomass resources playing a crucial but secondary role. The bioenergy sector of the effective cases is shaped by sophisticated and stable policy environments, often guided by long-term climate goals as well as EU-wide directives. Therefore, the motivation is shaped by scaling renewable energy to meet climate targets and ensure energy security. The most prominent policies constitute of feed-in tariffs or premiums and carbon taxes as well as mandatory biofuel share in electricity production (Banja et al., 2019; Cross et al.,

2021; Gustafsson and Anderberg, 2022). Within the transport sector, similar to the biomass-rich nations, obligations concerning fuel blending are applied (Ebadian et al., 2020) and subsidies serve as effective policy instrument in the heating sector (Banja et al., 2019).

Figure OD. 2 Building sector

In general, the description of effective policy cases within the buildings sector in the literature is with 4 out of 106 entry point rather scarce. We recognized that the entry point within the buildings sector differ mostly with regards to the deployment technology. Therefore, the clusters in Fig... represent the climate mitigation technology targeted by the entry point.

A central policy target within the building sector is to increase **energy efficiency**. We identified effective cases from the literature in the UK and Tokyo. In both regions emission reduction targets are set at the building sector level. The UK further sets emission reduction obligation for private actors like energy suppliers. Additionally, gas and electricity suppliers are required to implement energy-saving measures for domestic consumers in specific low-income areas, while the government supports payment schemes to reduce upfront costs for energy efficiency retrofits. The effectiveness of these measures appears to be facilitated by the rollout of smart meters (Trotta et al., 2018). In Tokyo, legally binding emission reduction targets for the building sector, coupled with strong administrative leadership, stakeholder involvement, flexible policy design, transparent monitoring, and gradual implementation, resulted in emission reductions in the buildings sector. These

reductions are primarily driven by to energy savings in office buildings through technological improvements (Roppongi et al., 2017).

Passive houses are a buildings concept of reduced energy consumption without universal definition and among others also referred to as net zero buildings (Liu et al., 2019). The effective policy cases in the literature focus on the passive house deployment policies in China (Liu et al., 2022, 2019). Economic growth objectives through the establishment of a local low-emissions buildings industry is centrally supported by international cooperation and technology transfer, particularly from Germany. This approach enabled a policy mix of investments in R&D, provision of grants and subsidies as well as land supply, to be effective.

In Sweden, rising prices for alternative heating options like oil and district heating, along with a general increase in electricity prices and carbon taxation increased the willingness to invest in **heat pumps**. In addition, local electric utilities along with public investments in R&D and an academic research continuity are decisive in knowledge creation and adaption of technological developments (Johansson, 2021).

Figure OD. 3 Less studied technologies

In a mixed-method approach, Kammermann (2018) analyse differences among cantons in Switzerland in their approaches to promoting **hydroelectricity**. The study identifies two effective pathways for strong hydroelectricity promotion. The first path involves large-scale hydroelectric production, a high level of resource exploitation, and ambitious climate goals. The second path combines a high level of exploitation with

strong left-wing and green political representation and similarly ambitious climate goals. In a study on China, Xie et al. (2022) statistically assess regional differences of the pilot program Carbon Emissions Trading Market on the effect of utilization of low-emission power generating sets, represented by hydropower. They find that the power generation technology structure in the eastern region is significantly better than that in the central-western region. They explain the difference with higher market maturity and economic development as well as scarcity of primary energy resources and high electricity demand in the eastern region.

California serves as best practice example for **behind-the-meter (BTM) energy storage** deployment. Where a high level of autonomy in energy governance has enabled the adoption of a variety of policy instruments to encourage the deployment of BTM storage (Shuai and Raufer, 2021). A key policy instrument includes procurement mandates and financial such as state-level rebate programs and federal tax credits.

Authoritarian regimes can reinforce nuclear policy goals by promoting positive narratives around expanding nuclear power. They can reduce potential tensions and conflicts in the early stages of anti-nuclear sentiment by emphasizing the benefits of increased nuclearization within the energy sector (Bourdais Park and Chung, 2022).

The best practice policy examples from UK and Norway illustrate who persistent and reliable policy support is necessary to promote deployment of high uncertainty technologies such as carbon management. Both examples are marked by multi stage funding and public demonstration projects. The UK applied a comprehensive policy mix— including R&D investments, carbon capture and storage (CCS) governmental office establishment and strategy as well as progress reports to ensure strategic policy communication (Inderberg and Wettestad, 2015). In Norway as well as in the UK, central enabling factors consist of sufficient resource availability (such as offshore storage capacity), commercial interest (from hard-to-abate sectors) and technological knowledge transfer (drawing from oil and gas industry). In addition, strong political interest and financial ability to invest in CCS, public support and ambitious climate targets served as enabling environment. Key lessons learned from Norway's demonstration projects highlight the importance of incorporating the entire carbon management chain—capture, transportation, and storage—within the project. Further, projects and technology risks need to be distributed among the project partners and well-defined incentives and business cases should be present for core actors (higher ETS prices, prospect to establish a European market for CO₂ and subsequently also a blue hydrogen market) (Wettestad et al., 2023).